

Environmental Impact Assessment of Civilian Armored Vehicles Produced in Europe

1. Overview of Environmental Legislation Affecting Armored Vehicles in Europe and Beyond

1a) Current European Legislation on Environmental Standards for Vehicles

Civilian armored vehicles in Europe are subject to rigorous environmental regulations, reflecting the region's commitment to reducing emissions and promoting sustainability across all industries. One of the key legislative frameworks governing environmental standards for vehicles is the Revised Clean Vehicles Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/1161). Adopted on June 20, 2019, and transposed into national law by August 2, 2021, this directive aims to foster clean mobility by promoting low- and zero-emission vehicles in public procurement processes.

Under the revised directive, the classification of a "clean vehicle" is determined by emissions thresholds and vehicle type. For light-duty vehicles (such as cars and vans), stringent CO₂ and nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emission standards apply. Until December 31, 2025, light-duty vehicles are required to emit no more than 50g/km of CO₂ and comply with up to 80% of the applicable real driving emissions (RDE) limits for NO_x. After January 1, 2026, only zero-emission vehicles will be classified as "clean." Heavy-duty vehicles (e.g., buses and trucks) may use alternative energy sources such as hydrogen, battery electric power, natural gas, liquid biofuels, synthetic fuels, and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG).

While this directive does include armored vehicles, it allows EU member states to grant exemptions from the clean energy requirements in national legislation. This exemption is crucial because armored vehicles typically require reinforced, heavier structures that increase fuel consumption and complicate compliance with emission limits. As a result, manufacturers often lobby for these exemptions to avoid meeting stringent emission standards, which may impact vehicle performance or raise production costs.

1b) Environmental Legislation for Civilian Armored Vehicles Outside the EU

In regions outside Europe, particularly in Africa and the Middle East, the environmental standards for civilian armored vehicles are generally less stringent. In these regions, considerations such as vehicle durability, cost-effectiveness, and resilience to extreme climates take precedence over emissions control. Many of these countries lack formal environmental regulations equivalent to those in the EU, allowing European manufacturers to export vehicles without retrofitting them to meet emissions standards. This regulatory divergence results in increased emissions from armored vehicles deployed outside the EU.

However, as part of global efforts to reduce emissions, some countries in the Middle East and Africa are beginning to adopt vehicle emissions regulations. Although these policies are typically less comprehensive and less strictly enforced than those in Europe, they represent a growing recognition of the need for environmental stewardship.

2. Major Civilian Armored Vehicle Manufacturers and Their Environmental Standards

European manufacturers of civilian armored vehicles are at the forefront of environmental innovation, driven by stringent regional regulations and the global demand for sustainable transportation solutions. These manufacturers are actively working to balance environmental performance with the structural and security demands of armored vehicles.

For example, vehicles that comply with EURO 4 standards, which have been in place since 2005, are available in European markets. These standards regulate pollutants from vehicle exhausts, setting emission limits for CO₂ and NO_x. Although EURO 4 standards have been superseded by more stringent EURO 5 and EURO 6 standards, some manufacturers, such as Centigon, offer vehicles that meet at least EURO 4 standards. These vehicles provide a compromise for markets that prioritize durability and resilience over the latest emissions controls.

Nonetheless, European manufacturers are increasingly focusing on hybrid and alternative fuel options to meet the region's evolving demand for low- and zero-emission vehicles. Recognizing the shift in customer expectations, companies are investing in research and development to enhance the

environmental efficiency of their armored vehicles. However, the transition remains gradual due to the inherent challenges of achieving energy efficiency and reducing emissions in heavily armored vehicles.

3. Alternative Solutions and Environmental Performance of Civilian Armored Vehicles

Given the challenges in achieving low emissions in armored vehicles, manufacturers are exploring several alternative solutions to mitigate their environmental impact. Some of these solutions include:

- **Hybrid and Electric Armored Vehicles:** European manufacturers are increasingly developing hybrid and fully electric armored vehicles. While hybrid-electric options offer the potential for reduced fossil fuel consumption and improved fuel efficiency, creating a battery system robust enough to support the weight and functionality of armored vehicles presents significant technical challenges.

- **Use of Alternative Fuels:** The use of biofuels, synthetic fuels, and hydrogen as alternatives to traditional diesel and petrol is another approach. Hydrogen fuel cells, in particular, offer a promising solution for emissions-free armored vehicles. However, the lack of widespread refueling infrastructure remains a key barrier to the widespread adoption of hydrogen-powered armored vehicles.

- **Lightweight Armor Materials:** Manufacturers are researching advanced materials such as composite armors and reinforced carbon fibers to reduce vehicle weight without compromising security. Lighter vehicles consume less fuel, thereby contributing to lower emissions over the vehicle's lifecycle.

- **Emissions Optimization Technology:** Retrofitting existing armored vehicles with emissions-reducing technologies, such as particulate filters, turbocharging, and advanced exhaust treatment systems, can help these vehicles meet EU emissions standards while extending their operational lifespan.

4. Implications for the European Defense Industry and Production Delocalization

As environmental considerations become increasingly integral to public procurement, the environmental performance of civilian armored vehicles will play a critical role in shaping the future of the European defense industry. This is particularly relevant given the potential for production delocalization to regions such as the Middle East, where environmental regulations are less stringent.

Delocalization presents both opportunities and risks. On one hand, relocating production to regions with less stringent emissions standards could reduce compliance costs. On the other hand, such a shift could undermine Europe's leadership in sustainable defense technology. If production moves to regions where emissions standards are not enforced, European manufacturers may lose their competitive advantage in an increasingly environmentally-conscious global market.

Ultimately, the European defense industry's commitment to sustainability in civilian armored vehicles will influence its future production strategies and market positioning. European companies will need to balance cost-effective manufacturing with regulatory compliance, while also continuing to innovate in sustainable practices.